

Optimizing Demand Paging using Profile Guided Function Positioning

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Optimering av virtuellt minne med hjälp av profilerad placering av funktioner

SAMMANFATTNING

När ett system använder virtuellt minne så är en av de viktigaste prestandaparametrarna antalet sidfel. Detta examensarbete presenterar en teknik för att minska antalet sidfel med så mycket som 20 – 40 %.

Det är viktigt att minimera antalet sidfel för de kan fördröja exekveringen betydligt. Det finns ett antal saker som kan göras för att uppnå en låg sidfelsfrekvens. Det mest uppenbara är att utöka storleken på RAM-minnet så att fler sidor får plats samtidigt. Detta är dock inte så särskilt lockande eftersom RAM-minne är dyrt. Ett annat sätt är att använda en bra sidbytnings-algoritm. Det är alltid fördelaktigt men vilken algoritm man än väljer så når den snabbt sina begränsningar. Något annat måste göras för att göra det hela ännu bättre. Mitt angreppssätt var att göra profilering och sen använda denna information till att möblera om kod på det sekundära minnet, på så sätt så att kod som användes mestadels "tillsammans" placerades på samma RAM-sida. I detta examensarbete presenterar jag hur jag inhämtade användbar profileringsinformation från ett realtidskritiskt system, och jag presenterar en ny metod för att möblera om koden, en metod som det i denna stund ligger en patentansökan på.

Undersökningen och testningen utfördes på en av Sony Ericssons mobiltelefoner, men metoden som presenteras för att möblera om kod är tillämplig på alla system som använder virtuellt minne. Den reducerade sidfelsfrekvensen kan användas till att öka exekveringshastigheten, öka storleken på det logiska minnet, minska storleken på RAM-minnet, eller någon kombination av dessa.

Optimizing Demand Paging using Profile Guided Function Positioning

ABSTRACT

When a system uses virtual memory one of the most important performance parameter is the page fault rate. This thesis present a technique to reduce the number of page faults by as much as 20 – 40 %.

It is important to keep the number of page faults as low as possible because they can delay the execution substantially. There are a number of things that can be done to achieve a low page fault rate. The most obvious is to extend the size of the RAM memory so that more pages can fit at the same time. This is however not so appealing because RAM memory is expensive. Another common technique is to use a good page replacement algorithm. This is always preferable but whatever algorithm is used it will soon reach its potential. Something else has to be done to make things even better. My approach was profiling, and then using this information to rearrange code on secondary memory so that code that was used mostly "together" was placed on the same page. In this thesis I present how I obtained useful profiling data in a real time critical system, and I present a new method for rearranging the code, a method that in this moment is patent pending.

The investigation and testing was carried out on a Sony Ericsson cellular phone, but the method presented to rearrange the code is applicable to any system that uses virtual memory.

The reduced page fault rate can either be used to increase execution speed, increase the size of the logical memory space, decrease the RAM memory size, or any combination of these.

FÖRORD

Jag, Rickard Möller, avlägger i följande uppsats en rapport om det examensarbete jag utfört på Sony Ericsson Mobile Communications AB i Lund och avdelningen Software System Engineering.

Jag vill framför allt tacka Tobias Ritzau, min handledare på Sony Ericsson Mobile Communications AB och Jonas Skeppstedt, min handledare på institutionen för datavetenskap vid Lunds universitet. Båda har bidragit till grundidén för examensarbetet och utan dem hade det inte blivit något.

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Alla dessa människor hjälpte mig att nå resultat som var långt över förväntan. Detta för ett projekt som det länge var tveksamt om det överhuvud taget skulle gå att genomföra.

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Rickard Möller

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ABBREVIATION LIST

RAM	Random Access Memory
CPU	Central Processing Unit
LRU	Least Recently Used
LRUA	Least Recently Used Approximation
FIFO	First In First Out
TLB	Translation Look-aside Buffer
PC	Program Counter
LR	Link Register

FACTUAL EXPLANATION

Virtual memory	Virtual memory is a method to create a more abstract memory management. The code or data doesn't necessary need to be loaded into RAM but can be placed in different storage devices.
Demand paging	Demand paging is a type of virtual memory where the desired data is loaded when it is needed. The data is composed into blocks of data (pages) of equal size and when a data item is needed the entire block of data is loaded.
Page	A page is a chunk of several data items within a given address interval. A page is also often called a page block or a RAM-page.
Thrashing	Thrashing occurs when page blocks are being excessively moved in and out of RAM. The CPU will be busy with all this moving of pages and will have little time to execute anything else. Thrashing is the result of a badly dimensioned paging system.
Working set	Working set is the collection of pages that a process is working with.
Spatial locality	A locality is a set of code or data that are actively used together. Spatial locality is the degree of which code or data whose addresses are close to one another is referenced close together in time.
Use case	Use case is a technical situation of common events used in a test.
Program counter	The program counter (PC) is a register that holds the current logical address of a programs execution.
Link register	The link register (LR) is a register that holds the logical address that a function should return to when finished.

1 INTRODUCTION

Computers of today have a rapid increase of processor-speed, but the memory-speed is not keeping up. The gap is widening. This makes it increasingly important to explore memory effectiveness.

There are mainly two software approaches to optimize the effectiveness of memory: to increase the cache memory hits or/and to reduce the page fault rate.

My approach and the work presented in this thesis is focused on the effectiveness of RAM memory in a virtual memory environment and thus to reduce the number of page faults. In most computer systems the page fault rate is currently minimized by generic page replacement algorithms, which try to model the temporal locality inherited in programs. By rearranging code at compile time there is a potential way to increase the spatial locality and to do the work easier for the page replacement algorithm.

1.1 PURPOSE

The purpose of this thesis is to investigate if it is possible to obtain useful profiling information from a cellular phone and, as a next step, if it is possible to use this information to reduce the number of page faults in a system using demand paging - not necessarily a demand paging environment for a cellular phone, but for demand paging systems in general.

The idea is to rearrange code on secondary memory in a way so that it makes the usage of RAM more effective. There is no grand rule on how to rearrange the code in an optimal fashion. But the basic approach is to rearrange the code so that code that are used "together" are placed close to each other in the physical address space, and to lift out code that very seldom is used (like error handling code) to another area of the address space. This should make the most used RAM-pages less "fragmented" and result in a smaller working set size and improve the spatial locality. With other words, the most used code will fit in fewer pages, thus reducing the page fault rate.

There is some work done in this area, and I will investigate how a "standard" method to rearrange code by Pettis and Hansen [1] performs, and try to make it better.

However, there are a lot of obstacles in the way. For instance it could turn out to be too difficult or impossible to obtain useful profiling information from a cellular phone. The most obvious problem is that there are a lot of real time critical operations done in a phone and the profiling will of course slow down the execution, and potentially trigger a lot of error handling code that normally wouldn't be used. And thus the profiling would be unreliable.

Another problem about the profiling is the vast quantity of code in the whole system of a cellular phone (somewhere in the magnitude of 100.000 functions). It could be very time-consuming or impossible to obtain profiling that is general enough to use for code rearranging. The reordered code has to perform good on a near infinity of different use-cases.

A more practical problem about profiling is how to obtain it from a cellular phone.

When the code finally is rearranged it is to be tested in a simulator to compare the page fault rate before and after the optimization.

To summarize, the thesis answers the following questions:

- * Is it possible to obtain useful and reliable profiling from a cellular phone?
- * How do rearranging of code effect the page fault rate?
- * How do different strategies of rearranging code differ?
- * Is the rearranged code general enough to perform well on different use-cases, even if there's insufficient profiling on them?

1.2 SCOPE

To make this project feasible I worked only with whole functions. Thus the profiling was only for functions and when I rearranged code I moved whole functions as a chunk of code.

The rearranging of functions I actually didn't do either, I only did a simulation of how the system would perform with the rearranged functions.

I only worked with data that was read only, and consisted mostly of code. This made the simulation of the demand-paging environment a bit easier; no pages had to be written back to secondary memory, since it couldn't be altered.

1.3 REPORT OUTLINE

This thesis is divided into the following five parts:

- * Chapter 2 - Theory presents the fundamentals concerning virtual memory and demand paging. It also describes terms concerning code layout.
- * Chapter 3 - Methodology describes what I have done and how I did it.
- * Chapter 4 - Results presents the results from the testing.
- * Chapter 5 - Discussion is an analysis of the results and what conclusions can be made from them.
- * Chapter 6 - Conclusion presents the final conclusions of this thesis and suggests further work that could be interesting to do in this area of research.

2 THEORY

2.1 VIRTUAL MEMORY

A long long time ago programmers had to make programs that fitted into the RAM memory of the system. If the application needed more RAM than the system could provide it resulted in a system crash. To avoid this problem, programmers configured their applications to only load the part of the application that was needed at the moment. This took a lot of effort and led to less focus on the actual application. Virtual memory was created so the computer's operating system took care of this instead of the programmer.

Virtual memory means that the parts that are needed at the moment are loaded into RAM. When the RAM memory is full some parts are moved back to the secondary storage to be replaced by another part of memory. This creates an abstraction of the RAM, making it seem as if it almost hasn't got any upper limit. This process is completely transparent to the applications.

Virtual memory is normally implemented with demand paging but can also be implemented with a segmentation system [4]. The main difference between these two approaches is that in a segmented system the memory is divided into blocks of varying sizes while paging uses the same size for all parts of memory. In this thesis I will only use the terminology of a paging system, but the basic ideas applies to segmented systems as well.

2.2 DEMAND PAGING

Demand paging is the type of virtual memory that is divided into fixed sized pages. A whole page is loaded into memory when a data item placed on that page is required. This is because the data that lies close to the required data is often needed in the near future. This is called the principle of locality, explained in Section 2.6.

The CPU addresses the memory with logical addresses. Logical addresses are not bound to a specific position in hardware; they have to be translated to physical addresses that are used in the memory space. This makes it easier to move memory to and from RAM without affecting the CPU.

The translation is done using a page table, which translates the logical address into a physical address. This translation notices if the given data is currently in RAM memory or stored on the secondary memory. Memory management often uses a small cache to speed up the translation process, and that is called a translation look-aside buffer or TLB. The TLB contains the last used translations, which according to the principle of locality are highly probable to be used in the near future.

Figure 2:1 – Demand paging.

The following is a possible scenario when a page is moved into the RAM memory:

1. The CPU requires a data item.
2. The address to the data is translated from the logical address space to the physical.
3. The address is searched for in the TLB, but it isn't found.
4. The address is searched for in the page table as well but isn't found there either.
5. A page-fault interrupt is triggered by the operating system.
6. The interrupt handler sees if there are any available pages in the page table, but there aren't.
7. A page replacement algorithm is run and finds a victim page to unload.
8. If the data in the victim page has been changed it is written back to the secondary memory, otherwise it can simply be overwritten.
9. The page that contains the necessary data is copied from secondary memory to RAM into the position that the old page had.
10. The translation data is updated.
11. The CPU restarts the event that required the data, and this time it finds the data.

The advantages of demand paging (virtual memory) are a larger memory space and the possibility to transparently execute applications from secondary memory. The disadvantage is delay caused by page faults. The number of page faults that occur is basically dependent on the size of the logical and physical memory, the algorithm for selecting the victim page, and the layout of data and code.

2.3 PERFORMANCE OF A DEMAND PAGING SYSTEM

There are several parameters that measure the performance of a demand paging system. A general formula used to measure the performance of a demand paging system is:

$$Memoryaccess_{effective} = Time_{NoPagefault} \cdot (1 - Rate_{Pagefault}) + Time_{Pagefault} \cdot Rate_{Pagefault}$$

Where the following parameters are:

- * $Memoryaccess_{Effective}$ = the estimated mean time to obtain a data item from the memory.
- * $Time_{NoPageFault}$ = the time it takes to obtain a data item when no page-fault occurs.
- * $Rate_{Pagefault}$ = a percent value of how often a page-fault occurs.
- * $Time_{PageFault}$ = the time it takes to obtain a data item when a page-fault occurs.

The central part of the equation is the page fault rate, which is affected by all parts of a demand paging system.

In a well-adjusted paging system there should be a balance between the amount of page faults and the size of RAM. If there are too many page faults then the system will use most of its time to move pages in and out of the memory, so called thrashing. Too few page faults mean that there is a rather large RAM memory and that it perhaps doesn't need to be that large.

The $Time_{PageFault}$ is also an interesting parameter. It shows how long time the system will pause to collect a page from the secondary storage. These pauses are short and are seldom detectable for a human but can be dangerous when many occur in a small time period. It is therefore not only interesting to know how long time a page fault takes but also when they appear. Do they occur all at once or are they evenly spread out over the execution time? If many page faults occur in a small time period it can stop the system for a longer time than it would for the same amount of page faults but spread out on a longer time period. This is because when a process is waiting for a page, another process gets to run, but if many processes are waiting for pages at the same time no processes at all can run, and we have thrashing.

The previous formula can be expressed even more detailed. The $Time_{NoPageFault}$ parameter is in fact composed of the following formula:

$$Time_{NoPagefault} = Lookup_{TLB} + Time_{RAMAccess} \cdot (1 - HitRate_{TLB})$$

Where the following parameters are:

- * $Time_{NoPageFault}$ = the time it takes to obtain a data item when no page-fault occurs.
- * $Lookup_{TLB}$ = the time it takes to lookup an address in the TLB.
- * $Time_{RAMAccess}$ = the time it takes to retrieve a page from RAM.
- * $HitRate_{TLB}$ = the percentage value that the data item is located in the TLB.

All these times are a lot shorter than the times regarding page faults. But if the TLB is badly dimensioned and the $HitRate_{TLB}$ are low then these values will be noticeable in the system [4].

All these aspects have to be considered to get a well-adjusted paging system. The best result is retrieved by knowing how the system behaves in all situations, to have statistics of how many page-faults occur at a certain load and how long time all parts in the paging process take.

2.4 PAGE REPLACEMENT ALGORITHMS

When the RAM memory is full and a new page needs to be loaded there has to be a page that is replaced. The question is which page. The best solution would be to replace the page that won't be used for the longest time, but it is difficult to predict which one that is [4]. Usually a generic page replacement algorithm is used which tries to model the temporal locality of programs. The Least Recently Used (LRU) algorithm is considered to be the de facto standard strategy for this task [10], meaning that it usually is the first choice if it is possible to use. However, it is often not possible to use because it needs much hardware support to decide which page that was least recently used, hardware support that many of today's computer systems don't provide.

Alternative algorithms are often used instead. To come as close to the performance of the LRU algorithm as possible there are algorithms that approximates the LRU algorithm. These are designed to use as little hardware support as possible. There are many Least Recently Used Approximation (LRUA) algorithms, such as Second Chance [4] and Aging to name a few. The one that requires the least hardware support is the Second Chance algorithm, which only uses one reference bit per page table entry. If the system has no hardware support at all then even simpler algorithms must be used. One of the simplest algorithms is to simply replace a random page. Another algorithm is to replace the pages in order, as a queue. This algorithm is generally called FIFO, which stands for First In First Out. There are several other algorithms but the ones described above are the most common.

The simulator that I used to simulate a demand-paging environment [11] had support for five different algorithms:

- * Optimal
- * Least Recently Used (LRU)
- * Least Recently Used Approximation (LRUA, Second Chance)
- * Random selection
- * First in First Out (FIFO)

The Optimal algorithm represents the optimal case when it replaces the page that will be used furthest into the future, and is only possible to use in a simulated environment. This is because a regular system, naturally, can't see into the future. However, it is good to have as a reference in a simulator.

2.5 WORKING SET

The working set is an approximation of an application's or a system's locality. It is the collection of pages that a process is working with, and which must be resident if the process is to avoid thrashing [4]. A working set is, strictly, the set of unique pages that a process is working with during a specific time period, for example 1 second. So it is a moving window of pages. However, when I mention working set in this thesis I do not mean the strict definition. Instead I use a simplified where I don't look at each process, but the working set for all processes combined. This is because I couldn't get any information on which process that was using a specific page during the verification test, due to a limitation in the logic analyzer (see Section 3.2.2). Anyway, this combined working set is also interesting; it gives information on how the overall set of used pages vary during execution.

2.6 THE PRINCIPLE OF LOCALITY

Programs tend to reuse data and instructions that they used recently. The locality model states that when a process executes, it moves from locality to locality [4]. A locality is a set of code or data that are actively used together. A program is generally composed of several different localities, which may overlap. An implication of locality is that one can predict with reasonable accuracy what instructions and data a program will use in the near future based on its accesses in the recent past. This is used by the page replacement algorithm and is the whole idea for a working cache memory.

There are two types of localities (time and space):

- * Temporal locality Temporal locality states that recently accessed items are likely to be accessed in the near future (time).
- * Spatial locality Spatial locality says that items whose addresses are near one another tend to be referenced close together in time (space).

A widely held rule of thumb is that a program spends 90% of its execution time in 10% of the code [9]. Since this 10% of code not necessarily is contiguous in memory, a program spends that 90% of its execution time requesting considerably more than 10% of its total number of pages [8].

The basic idea presented in this thesis is to rearrange code so that the spatial locality improves. In doing so, a fewer number of pages are requested more often, thereby decreasing the working set size and hence decreasing the page fault rate.

2.7 OPTIMAL CODE LAYOUT

Functions are normally laid out by the linker in the order that they are encountered. The resulting code layout would seem to be quite random, and it is from the linker's point of view. However, functions that originally come from the same source file normally get placed next to each other. This gives the layout some spatial locality when functions from the same source file tend to often call each other.

In this thesis I tried to minimize the number of page faults by rearranging the order of functions on secondary memory. But what layout is the best? What order of functions should I choose? Unfortunately no one knows. Well, for very small programs it is possible to come up with the optimal layout, if the profiling is perfect. But in this project I worked with a whole system with a vast code size (in the magnitude of 100.000 functions). And the fact is that to find the optimal layout of code is not only NP-hard, but it is also poorly approximable [7]. In Chapter 3 I will describe what heuristics I used.

To get a better understanding of the importance and potential of rearranging of code I present a simple example. We have the following program with four functions:

Figure 2:2 – An example of code rearranging

If execution starts in function A, the CPU demands code from functions in this order:

A D A D A D A B C B C B A

Now let's say that we have a very small RAM and that, for simplicity, it is divided only into one RAM-page. If the code is placed on secondary memory as in Layout 1 it will result in 11 page faults. But if we choose Layout 2 instead it will stop at only 3 page faults.

The extremely improved result for Layout 2 is easy to explain. If you look at the program you see that function A calls D 3 times. In Layout 1, A and D is placed on different pages, so page 1 and 2 have to be exchanged every time A calls D and every time D returns to A, resulting in 6 page faults for that part. In Layout 2, A and D happens to be on the same page. The same situation occurs for B and C.

Though this was an exaggerated example it shows the potential and importance of code placement on secondary memory.

2.8 PROFILING

Profiling is a method to obtain information about what parts of the code that are used when a program executes. Depending on what type of profiling that is done the obtained information can be from a counter on some part of the code to a complete call-tree. But typically the profiling is based on functions (it is in this thesis) and is intended to produce a call-tree.

The profiling can be dependent on different use-cases and vary in quality. If there are many different possible use-cases in a program, there has to be profiling done on every one of them to get complete profiling-information. But even this is not perfect because the different use-cases may not be used equally often. This leads to the conclusion that profiling almost always is an approximation, with a degree of reliability.

3 METHODOLOGY

It is clear from Section 2.3 that the amount of page faults is the most important performance parameter in a demand paging system. Much could be gained by decreasing that amount, and the goal of this project was to do just that.

3.1 PROJECT OVERVIEW

In this project there were distinct steps and each had to be accomplished before going to the next.

Step 1 - Insert profiling code

There was no existing method to obtain the kind of profiling-information that was needed from the Sony Ericsson cellular phone that I made the testing on. So to be able to do profiling on the code I had to develop programs that inserted profiling-code into the functions in the source code of the system. Then recompile it, link it and flash over the new system to the phone.

Step 2 - Produce profiling logs

To get profiling logs the phone was hooked up with a logic analyzer. This recorded writes to specific variables, writes triggered by the profiling-code.

Step 3 - Make the call tree

The logs from Step 2 contained lists of addresses. Those addresses were mapped against the functions involved by use of a symbol table. A call tree could then be produced.

Step 4 - Get an optimal function order

The call tree was fed to a function-ordering algorithm that produced a preferable order of functions.

Step 5 - Produce testing logs

The phone was hooked up to the logic analyzer again, but with a system without any profiling. This time all addresses that were sent from RAM to the CPU were recorded.

Step 6 - Simulate the new order of functions

To make a simulation of the rearranging of code I copied the logs from step 5 and altered the addresses to reflect the new order of functions.

Step 7 - Test it

An existing simulator of a demand paging system was used for this task. It was developed in another master thesis project by Marcus Andersson [11]. As input it got the logs from step 5 and 6, and it output the number of page faults, among other things. This way there was a method to compare the performance before and after my rearranging of code.

3.2 PROFILING

If we look ahead a little, what information is needed by an algorithm that is supposed to find a preferable order of functions? Well it depends on how it works, but in this case it wants to know how many times a specific function calls another specific function. To get that information there have to be some sort of profiling done. Unfortunately there was no existing method to obtain that kind of profiling from the Sony Ericsson cellular phone that I made the testing on. So I had to do that from scratch.

In a cellular phone there is a lot of real time critical code. The profiling must not delay this code too much because then the profiling would be wrong; the critical operations could exceed their deadlines resulting in execution of a lot of error-handling code. This would make the profiling unreliable and not reflect a typical execution. With this in mind there had to be a decision made on how to obtain the profiling. It was decided that profiling-code was to be inserted into the functions on an assembly code level and that this profiling-code should write to a few “profiling-variables”. A logic analyzer could then record those writes. This way it would delay the execution only the time it took to write to those variables and the logic analyzer is an outside observer that doesn’t effects the execution in the phone. Another advantage with assembler code was that it could be machine-generated, so it was fairly easy to parse.

The profiling-code was to be inserted at the start of functions and just before every return from functions. The code should write the current program counter (PC) to a special variable which we call a “super” global variable, meaning that it is visible for the whole system. It also should write the current process id to another variable. The resulting profiling would then be a list of addresses and which process an address belonged to for the moment. From this list a call-tree later can be constructed, explained in Section 3.2.4.

I had access to only about 32% of the source code for the whole system (which still is a vast quantity of code). So it was only possible to insert profiling in this 32% of the code. But as the results in Chapter 4 will show, even this incomplete profiling made improved result for the whole system.

3.2.1 INSTRUMENTING OF CODE

To instrument the code I made a program that acted as the compiler in the build process. This program first generated an assembler file by calling the real compiler with the appropriate options. The assembler format was ARM [5][6]. ARM is designed to save space. There are two kinds of instruction-sets: ARM and Thumb. An ARM instruction is a 32-bit instruction and is the faster of the two; it is used in time-critical operations. The Thumb instruction is a 16-bit instruction and is used to save space.

My program then inserted profiling-code into the generated assembler file at the start of functions and just before every return in the functions (the inserted code actually was a call to a special profiling-function, detailed described in Section 3.2.3). Finally my program compiled the altered assembler file by calling the real compiler again with the assembler file as input.

When executing, the inserted profiling-code wrote the current logical address (PC), to a specific super global variable. It also wrote the current process id to another variable. Because the phone that was used not had any virtual memory, the logical and physical addresses happened to be the same. So the PC could be directly mapped to an address in a symbol table (Section 3.2.4).

This all may seem quite simple, but I encountered a seemingly endless number of problems along the way. To mention a few:

- * In assembler code there is long and short jumps to other functions or other parts of the code. Short jumps are preferable because they can be performed with fewer or shorter instructions. When I inserted code, some of the short jumps became too long because of the extended code size. This could first be detected when the altered assembler file was compiled. The solution was to make my program detect the failed compiling, parse the error message and then alter the jump from a short to a long. But it does not end here; when a jump is altered from a short to a long it brings with it that more code have to be inserted and potentially conflict with other short jumps that passed the first time. So this was done over and over until the compiler was satisfied.
- * There are various data mixed with the code. This data have to be aligned to an even 32-bit address. Much of the code that was inserted was thumb code (16 bits instructions), so sometimes the alignment of the data went off by 16 bits. The solution was to insert an extra thumb-NOP before the badly aligned data. This was also done over and over until the compiler was satisfied.
- * Certain kinds of data that is loaded by instructions have to be within a given range from the load instruction. The inserted code often placed that data out of range. There was no way to change this instruction in a similar way as with short and long jumps. Instead I copied the data to a closer position, with a new label, and then changed the label of the load instruction to the new one.
- * Some jumps inside a function (like in switch statements) was made static by the compiler, meaning that instead of a jump instruction to a label the jump was performed by adding a constant offset to the PC. And as you might guess, the inserted code made those offsets all wrong sometimes. This was a quite tricky problem because this error was not detected when the altered assembler file was compiled. The solution was to look for those "PC-jumps" and not alter the size of the code between the jump and the target. The code that I had to insert was just before every return, so I exchanged the return to a jump (the jump-instruction was the same size as the return-instruction) outside of the "PC-jump"-area and inserted the profiling code there and made the return.

This was some of the major problems. The build process took about two hours so to fix all those problems where quite time consuming and represented a big part of the total time spent on this project.

3.2.2 CREATING LOGS WITH A LOGIC ANALYZER

The logs that I used where created using a logic analyzer. It could be triggered to log a number of different things. When I made the profiling it was triggered to log the data that was written to the "profiling-variables" (the PC and the process id), i.e. it was triggered when data was written to the addresses of those variables. These addresses were known from a map-file (symbol table) that the linker produced.

When I made logs to verify the results (Section 3.4) the logic analyzer was triggered to log all the addresses of executing code that the CPU retrieved from the RAM memory.

The logging time varied in length but in general the logs (for both profiling and verifying) were created from a few minutes of execution.

There was a “bug” in the logic analyzer, a “bug” that most likely was caused by that the analyzer was pushed to its limits. The logic analyzer had previously been used with other phone models without any problems. But the phone that I worked with had overall a little faster performance. This made the analyzer to miss the triggering in some cases. When the CPU transferred 32 bits of data (a normal integer) to the RAM it was written as two individual 16 bits of data continuously after each other. Sometimes (about 5% of the times) the analyzer only triggered on the first 16 bits (the 16 low bits) of that data and missed the other half. There couldn’t be any pattern detected in this so it happened seemingly random. This was a problem when making profiling logs because the logical address and the process id that was written to my “profiling-variables” consisted of 32 bits. And when making verification logs it ruined the possibility to get information on which process that currently was running. But it did luckily not destroy the logging of addresses of executing code that the CPU retrieved from the RAM memory, because those were just addresses and not data. This made this a severe problem only for the profiling part. How it was solved is described in Section 3.2.3.

For the profiling I made 38 different logs on typical tasks on the phone. In this profiling 33% of the profiled code was “touched”, or 10% of all the code. This indicates that 67% of the profiled code very infrequently is used and should be lifted out to an isolated area of the address space.

3.2.3 THE PROFILING CODE

To get around the problem about the “half-writes” mentioned in previous Section, a “hack” was made in the assembly code that wrote the PC and process id to the “profiling-variables”. Instead of writing the data only ones to one variable, it wrote the same data twice to two different variables, but with the data shifted down 16 bits when writing the second time. This made it possible to reconstruct the complete data written even if the triggering would fail. It was a simple task to later go through the logs and take the 16 low bits from the two variables, shift up one of them and then make a bitwise or to reconstruct the wanted data.

The profiling-code that was inserted into the assembler files is presented below. Into the functions I inserted calls like this at the start of the function and just before every return:

```
MOV    R12,LR                ;; saving LR
BLX    profiler_func_start_or_return
MOV    LR,R12                ;; restoring LR
```

When calling my “profiling-function” the LR (Link Register, the return address) became the PC that I wanted to save. The original LR got overwritten when the call was made so that had to be stored. The jump to the “profiling-function” in the start of functions **always** had to be the second instruction because the stored PC had to be a fixed offset into the function, this to later be able to conclude that a certain logged address was an entering of a function and not a return. The “profiling-function” consisted of the following code:

```

CODE32
profiler_func_start_or_return:
    STMDB    SP!,{R0,R1}                ;; Pushing registers R0 and R1 to the stack so they can be used
    MRS     R0,CPSR                     ;; Disable interrupts (moving PSR to General-purpose register)
    AND     R1,R0,#0xC0
    CMP     R1,#0xC0                    ;; Is IRQ and FIQ bit set?
    BEQ     ??dont_disable_interrupts   ;; Already disabled, do no need to disable again
    ORR     R0,R0,#0xC0                 ;; Set IRQ and FIQ bit
    MSR     CPSR_c,R0                   ;; Interrupts disabled (move to Status Register from ARM Register)
    LDR     R0,??profiler_func_start_or_return_0 ;; Loading address of process id
    LDR     R1,[R0,#0]                  ;; Loading value of process id
    LDR     R0,??profiler_func_start_or_return_0+4 ;; Loading address of the "process id low"-variable
    STR     R1,[R0, #+0]                ;; Store process id to "process id low"
    MOV     R1,R1, LSR #+16             ;; R1 = R1 >>> 16
    STR     R1,[R0, #+4]                ;; Store high bits of process id to "process id high"
    STR     LR,[R0, #+8]                ;; Store LR (PC) to "current pc low"
    MOV     R1,LR, LSR #+16             ;; R1 = LR >>> 16
    STR     R1,[R0, #+12]               ;; Store high bits of LR to "current pc high"
    MCR     p15, 0, R0, c7, c10, 1    ;; Clean data cache line (force writing to RAM)
    MRS     R0,CPSR                     ;; Enable interrupts
    BIC     R0,R0,#0xC0                 ;; Clear IRQ and FIQ bit
    MSR     CPSR_c,R0                   ;; Interrupts enabled
    LDMIA   SP!,{R0,R1}                ;; Restoring R0 and R1
    BX     LR                            ;; Return
??dont_disable_interrupts:
    LDR     R0,??profiler_func_start_or_return_0
    LDR     R1,[R0,#0]
    LDR     R0,??profiler_func_start_or_return_0+4
    STR     R1,[R0, #+0]
    MOV     R1,R1, LSR #+16
    STR     R1,[R0, #+4]
    STR     LR,[R0, #+8]
    MOV     R1,LR, LSR #+16
    STR     R1,[R0, #+12]
    MCR     p15, 0, R0, c7, c10, 1
    LDMIA   SP!,{R0,R1}
    BX     LR
DATA
??profiler_func_start_or_return_0:
    DC32    +0x4C048778                 ;; Address of variable containing the process id
    DC32    +0x4C182420                 ;; Address of "process id low" and it is an even cacheline-address

```

The instructions from this “profiling-function” could of course be inserted directly into the code instead of making a call to it (inlining). That would maybe speed up the execution slightly because jumps take a relatively long time to perform. But it would also increase the total code size dramatically, which would make the code size to expand beyond certain strict limits. So it was out of the question.

3.2.4 MAKING THE CALL TREE

To make the call-tree and to retrieve the information about how many times a function calls another, I used the profiling-logs and a map-file (symbol table). The linker in the building process produced the map-file, and it is essentially a list of all the linked functions and data with their start and end addresses.

My program for this task went through the profiling logs and produced one call-tree for each process. This was done by mapping the address in the log against a function in the map-file. If the address was a certain offset from the start of the function then it could be concluded that this was an entering of the function, and the function was pushed on a stack. Otherwise it must have been a return from the function, and then the function should be at the top of the stack, and was popped. When a function (B) was to be pushed to the stack, it was known that the function currently on top of the stack (A) must have been the caller. So function A got added with a call to function B.

There where of course many different processes in the system running at the same time, and to make correct call-trees there had to be one made for each process, so there where one stack for every process. To separate the processes each logged address came with a process id.

Finally a list of functions was produced. Attached to each function was another list of functions that the function in question had called, and how many times it had been called. This list could then be fed to a function-ordering algorithm, Section 3.3.

3.3 FUNCTION POSITIONING

To find out an optimal order of functions is the central piece of this thesis. A new algorithm was developed for this purpose. The new algorithm is similar to the procedure-ordering algorithm by Pettis and Hansen [1] but with some modifications, and those modifications made significantly improved results. From now on I will refer to the algorithm by Pettis and Hansen as PH. I first implemented PH to get a feel for how rearranging of functions effected the page fault rate. When those results not where as good as I had hoped I did some brainstorming and came up with a much better algorithm. Though I came up with that algorithm my self, it was a little inspired from different cache optimizing techniques [2][3][7][8].

3.3.1 THE ALGORITHM BY PETTIS AND HANSEN

The function positioning algorithm by Pettis and Hansen [1] is known as the “reference standard” in this area of research. It goes by the principle that “closest is best”. In other words, functions that call each other often should end up close to each other in the final code. The idea is that this should increase the chance that they will be placed on the same RAM-page, thus reducing the working set size and thereby reducing the number of page faults.

The first step in PH is to build an undirected weighted call graph by using the collected profiling data. Each node contains a list of functions, but initially this list contains only one function. Edges correspond to the calls between these functions. The weight of edges is the sum of the number of calls made between the connected functions. Calls made from a function to itself (recursion) are skipped. Figure 3:1 on page 23 illustrates an initial graph.

When the graph is built, a loop is started. At each loop the most weighted edge is removed from the graph (if weights are equal one is arbitrary chosen). The nodes connected by this edge get merged into one node. Remaining edges leaving each node are coalesced (weights are simply summarized). When nodes are merged the two lists of functions get connected. This process continues until all edges are removed from the graph, and remaining is one or more nodes. Now the loop ends.

The last step is to produce a function-order list. If the graph contains only one node this is very simple, the list wanted is the list of functions in the node. If more than one node is in the graph then the list of functions in each node is arbitrary connected.

The merging of nodes need further clarification, there are essentially two cases:

1. The two nodes contain only one function each:

In this case the two lists of functions can be arbitrary connected. Let's say we have function A in node 1 and function B in node 2. The merged node will contain a list with two functions and the order can be AB or BA. Which we choose is not of any concern when the important thing is that A and B are as close to each other as they can be.

2. One or both of the nodes contain more than one function:

Here consideration is taken to which ends the lists get connected. Let's say that node 1 contains function A and B, and that node 2 contains function C and D. There are four different ways to construct the new list:

AB-CD
AB-DC
BA-CD
BA-DC

To decide on one, a look is taken on the original weight between the functions. The most weighted of B-C, B-D, A-C and A-D decides. So if A-C is the most weighted of the four, the lists are connected so that A and C gets as close as possible to each other, thus BA-CD is chosen (or DC-AB that is seen as similar).

To explain further how the PH-algorithm works I present a complete example in Figure 3:1 to Figure 3:8.

Figure 3:1 - Original graph. Each node contains one function and edges correspond to the number of calls made between those functions.

Figure 3:2 - After 1 loop. Nodes F and H gets merged. When choosing the next edge to remove there are two choices; both have weight 8, one is arbitrary chosen.

Figure 3:3 - After 2 loops.

Figure 3:4 - After 3 loops.

Figure 3:5 - After 4 loops.

Figure 3:6 - After 5 loops.

Figure 3:7 - After 6 loops. When these two nodes get merged in the next loop there is not any preferable ends on which the lists of functions get connected. So one is arbitrary chosen. This is because there are no calls made between either of BD, BG, ED or EG. With my new algorithm there is a distinct best choice here.

Figure 3:8 - After 7 loops. The final node and order of functions. If this had been a graph with "islands" there had been a set of nodes here without any edges between them.

3.3.2 MY NEW ALGORITHM

The new code-layout (order of functions) retrieved from the PH-algorithm did not achieve good results. Sometimes the amount of page faults was decreased but most of the time it made things worse. The PH-algorithm did clearly not work on the system I made the testing on. Why didn't it? The answer to that I do not know. It should, at least in theory, make a slight improvement. While thinking about this I got an idea for a new algorithm. The new algorithm is based on the PH-algorithm, but with some crucial changes. With this new algorithm the amount of page-faults was dramatically reduced compared to both the original code-layout and the one retrieved with the PH-algorithm. More about the results is to be read in Chapter 4.

My supervisor at Sony Ericsson thought that the results from this algorithm were interesting enough to file for a patent. So the method used in the algorithm is in this moment patent pending. Unfortunately this also means that I not can reveal any details about my new algorithm at this time.

3.4 SIMULATION

To test how the new order of functions would perform in a demand paging environment a simulation was done. In order to do the simulation I first produced logs from a system without any profiling. The logs contained all addresses of data that were sent from RAM to the CPU. The logic analyzer was used to produce these logs, see Section 3.2.2.

3.4.1 SIMULATING THE NEW CODE LAYOUT

To simulate the new order of functions (the new code layout determined by one of the function positioning algorithms) a new log was produced by feeding a program with the original log, the profiled order of functions and a map-file. The program went through the original log and mapped every address against a function in the map-file. By use of the new order of functions, an offset could be calculated that that function should be moved. The address then was added with this offset and the altered address was written to the new log.

However, because of the CPU-cache there was a small limitation in this procedure. The logic analyzer actually only could see addresses of data that were sent from RAM to the CPU-cache. This means that when the CPU demands data on a specific address, not only that data is transferred to the CPU, but the whole cache-line of data that contains the data wanted. A cache-line is a block of contiguous data, typically 32 bytes in size.

So when the program looked at the log there could be addresses whose data never actually got used. If this is in the middle of functions it is not a problem but if the cache-line overlaps two functions it is impossible to know which one of the functions that actually was used, it could be both or just one of them. This was something that couldn't be ignored because it would corrupt the new log in a way so it yielded considerable more page faults than it should. Let me try and explain why with the help of Figure 3:9.

Figure 3:9 – An example of how the layout of code can change. There are two RAM-pages containing seven functions, A to G, with constant sizes. Each page is divided into eight cache-lines.

If the CPU is about to execute function B it will start with demanding the code at the start of the function. This is the end of cache-line 3 in the unchanged code layout (the original log). Because of how the cache works all of the code in cache-line 3 will be transferred to the CPU-cache, meaning that all of those addresses will show up in the log. The result of this is that addresses belonging to function A also will appear in the log, even if it wasn't used. In the case of the unchanged code layout this will not affect the number of page faults because the whole cache-line always is on the same RAM-page. But when I alter the addresses in the log to reflect the new code layout, function A and B might get placed on different RAM-pages, as they are in the new code layout in Figure 3:9. This may yield a page fault for function A, if that page not already is in RAM. This is wrong because A was never actually used.

The conclusion of this is that all addresses in cache-lines that overlap functions are unreliable. To fix this problem I simply removed all such addresses, from both the original and the new log. The removal of those addresses does not affect the number of page faults except maybe in two cases:

1. When only one or two cache-lines contain the whole function, and those cache-lines overlaps functions, that function is totally removed. This is the case for function E, but not for F that is of equal size. And if the removed function happens to be on a RAM-page that not currently is loaded into RAM there is a missed page fault.
2. When the first or last cache-line is "alone" on another RAM-page there also can be a missed page fault. This is the case for function D.

However, this removal of cache-line addresses at start and end of functions should only very little, if anything, affect the comparison in number of page faults between the altered and unaltered code-layout. This is because the addresses are removed from both logs. But I make a small reservation about the validity of my results because of this and strongly recommend to make new tests with physically reordered code when or if this gets possible.

3.4.2 SIMULATION OF A DEMAND PAGING ENVIRONMENT

Now I had two different logs (Section 3.4.1), one with an unaltered code-layout and one with the profiled code-layout. To compare the differences in performance of those layouts I feed the logs to a simulator that simulated a demand paging environment. This simulator was developed in another master thesis project by Marcus Andersson [11]. The simulator output a number of things where the interesting for me was:

- * The number of page faults.
- * The time delay caused by page faults.
- * The number of pages used during a specific time period (working set size).

In the simulator it was possible to set the page size, the RAM size and what page replacement algorithm it should use.

4 RESULTS

In the intended demand paging system that I made the testing for, the size of the pages can be divided into 1, 4 or 64 kB pages. It also only has support for the page replacement algorithms FIFO and Random, where FIFO is the most likely to be used. In all the testing I did I found that the best overall performance could be found with a page size of 512 B or 1 kB, independent on which layout that was used. And in the thesis by Marcus Andersson [11] the conclusion was that a page size of 1 kB or 4 kB is preferable. This indicates that a page size of 1 kB will be used. So the most relevant results are the ones with a page size of 1 kB and where the page replacement algorithm FIFO is used. Because of this I will mostly present results that had those settings, so if I not explicitly mention anything about which page size or page replacement algorithm that was used in a test, it is 1 kB and FIFO.

Because I didn't have access to all of the source code (mentioned in Section 3.2) the testing is divided into two categories: one where the testing was made on all the code and one where it was made only on profiled code. When I altered the logs (Section 3.4.1) I also attached a flag to the address: is this address in a profiled part of the code or not. This made it easy to run the simulator in two "modes", one with all code and one where the unprofiled code was filtered out (with unprofiled I mean code that wasn't inserted with profiling-code). The full potential of the reordered code is shown when running only with profiled code, but with all code it will show how the reordering would perform if only parts of the code was profiled. Would it maybe make things worse than they where before? This wouldn't be good at all because it is often the case that one doesn't have access to all the source code, for example if library routines are used.

I did the measurements mainly on two different use cases:

Use case 1:

Startup, menu-walking, java, movie, music

Use case 2:

Outgoing and incoming call, radio

In use case 1 I tried to cover a typical use of the phone. Use case 2 is of special interest because there was deliberately not made any profiling on any calling or use of the radio (meaning that the used code for this might have profiling-code inserted but when collecting profiling-data, Section 3.2.2, I never made any call or used the radio). So it will show how the reordered code will perform with insufficient profiling data.

4.1 PAGE FAULT RATE

Figure 4:1 shows the number of page faults encountered with different RAM sizes. The test was done only on profiled code and with three different code layouts: one unchanged, one where the function order had been determined by the PH-algorithm and one where the function order came from my new algorithm. Those three different layouts of code I will from now on refer to as unchanged layout, PH-layout and my layout.

Figure 4:1 – Shows the performance with only the profiled code in use case 1. Three different code layouts were used: unchanged layout, layout determined by the PH-algorithm and layout determined by my new algorithm. The x-axis shows the RAM-size in percentage, where 100% is the amount of RAM needed for the unchanged layout to only encounter one page fault per page loaded.

In Figure 4:1 it can be concluded that with a RAM size over 100% there was only one page fault per page that was loaded; the interesting thing about this part is that it indicates the differences of the working set size (a momentarily working set size). Both the PH-layout and my layout initially give a smaller working set size, but when many page faults begin to occur the PH-layout is the one that mostly tends to cause trashing. This was quite surprising but it was the general behavior for the PH-layout in all of my testing.

Figure 4:2 – This is the same test as in Figure 4:1, but it shows the page faults as a percent value compared with the unchanged layout.

How can this result be translated into how much RAM that can be saved with my layout? Well this varies but I found a rule of thumb that seems to work quite well in all the testing I did. In the result presented in Figure 4:2, the average percent-value that my layout decreases the number of page faults with when the RAM size is under 100% is approximately 39%, compared to the unchanged layout. This can directly be translated to that my layout performs as good as the unchanged with 39% less RAM, and even with a little margin in some cases. This can be verified in Figure 4:1.

Figure 4:3 – Shows the performance with all code in use case 1.

Figure 4:4 – Shows the performance with all code in use case 1.

Figure 4:3 and Figure 4:4 show that my layout performs well even if 68% of the code is unprofiled (see Section 3.2 on page 17). Although this is good, there can not be drawn any absolute conclusion out of this because the profiled and unprofiled code mostly was separated already in the unchanged layout, as can be seen in Figure 4:8 on page 33.

Figure 4:5 – Shows the performance with all code in use case 1 with four different page replacement algorithms.

Figure 4:5 shows that the reordered code perform quite similarly compared to the unchanged independent of which page replacement algorithm that is used. In the figure all the four data series from the unchanged layout lays on top of each other on 0%.

Figure 4:6 – Shows the performance with only the profiled code for use case 2.

Figure 4:7 – Shows the performance with all code for use case 2.

Figure 4:6 and Figure 4:7 show the performance for use case 2. This was not a profiled use case, meaning that the code might have been touched by the profiling, but not in the context of use case 2. These results should be compared to the ones in Figure 4:2 and Figure 4:4. They are slightly inferior which is not a surprise, but still the result for my layout is considerably better compared to the unchanged. This indicates that my algorithm is quite forgiving against incomplete profiling data and/or that my profiling-data collected is very general.

4.2 MEMORY ACCESSES

Figure 4:8 - Shows how the memory is accessed during use case 1 with unchanged code layout. The resolution is quite low so each dot represents several pages. If one of those pages is accessed the dot gets colored. The vertical lines represent 60 seconds. Green dots are profiled code and red dots are unprofiled code. And with sharp eyes you can see blue dots; they are profiled code that wasn't touched by the profiling.

Figure 4:9 - Shows how the memory is accessed during use case 1 with PH-layout.

Figure 4:10 - Shows how the memory is accessed during use case 1 with my code layout.

It can be seen in Figure 4:10 that with my layout the most used code is concentrated to many local areas, those local areas are scattered out quite evenly over the address space. The big white gap is profiled code that wasn't "touched" during the collecting of profiling data. In the PH-layout on the other hand, Figure 4:9, it is clear that the most used code is concentrated only to one big area. This quite well illustrates how the two algorithms work.

4.3 PAGE SIZE

Figure 4:11 - Shows a comparison of the performance with different page sizes. The y-axis displays the total delay caused by page faults; see Section 2.3 for an explanation.

The best result that I encountered for use case 1 with my layout was amazingly 56% decrease of the page faults. This was with a page size of 4 kB, 30% RAM size, with the page replacement algorithm FIFO and only with profiled code. However, as you can see in Figure 4:11 the overall performance with a page size of 4 kB are quite bad, so that result is not very interesting. This figure also justifies the reasoning in the beginning of this Chapter about why I chose to present the most test results with a page size of 1 kB.

4.4 PAGE FAULTS OVER TIME

Figure 4:12 – Shows the page fault rate over time. The x-axis shows the time in a virtual time unit scale.

Figure 4:12 is a selected typical part of the execution in use case 1. It shows that the PH-layout and the unchanged layout are the ones that mostly tend towards trashing when many page faults occur in a small time period. This was the general behavior in all of the testing.

4.5 WORKING SET SIZE

Figure 4:13 – This chart shows a working set measurement spanning over 30 seconds.

In Figure 4:13 I choose to present a working set size spanning over 30 seconds because this gave the clearest chart. I also made tests with working set sizes spanning over 1, 15 and 60 seconds. The pattern however was the same. And the pattern is that the working set size is substantially decreased with my layout, but actually a little bigger for the PH-layout, which was surprising.

5 DISCUSSION

My results show that the selected approach to optimize the effectiveness of memory by rearranging code based on profiling can be successful.

It was possible, although with some problems, to obtain useful profiling information from a cellular phone. The profiling method selected did not delay the execution so much that it changed its behavior. The real time critical code did not exceed their deadlines, because if it had it would clearly show as bad results for the reordered code, the error handling code would perform very well, but in my verification tests not any (or very little) of that code is executed.

The relatively small amount of profiling-data that I retrieved was general enough to cover a large size of different use cases. The result from a practically unprofiled use case indicates this (use case 2). But still there is a large room for improvement here. The profiling is very important and more is always better.

The method to obtain profiling with the help of a logic analyzer works but is quite time-consuming and destroys the possibility to make a large scale profiling in the field. The ideal would be to have a number of phones with profiled code in them, distribute them to typical users and let them use the phone for maybe a month. Then collect the profiling information from them.

The choice of method to rearrange the code is of uttermost importance. For example, the layout produced by the PH algorithm often made things worse, while the layout retrieved with my new algorithm always reduced the page fault rate. The results presented in the article about the PH algorithm [1] say that it should improve a program's performance with around 7 – 10 % (measured in time), by reducing the amount of page faults and long jumps. Why didn't it work in the testing done in this thesis? The answer to that may be that the tests done in the article was on relatively small programs, while the testing done in this thesis was on a very big system.

5.1 PRACTICAL ISSUES AND SUGGESTIONS

The method that I used to insert profiling-code into the source code and to retrieve profiling-data is quite experimental and not very practical. If this is to be used for real in the development of a cellular phone all this have to be made much simpler. I have a few suggestions about how it could be done:

- * I used a quite simple technique to insert profiling-code into the assembler files. The program that did this did not keep track of any sizes or offsets. This did cause a lot of compiler errors due to the extended code size. I manage to fix every one of them but with a little altered source code there is no guarantee that it will continue to work. Much better would be to get support in the compiler so that it could insert the extra profiling-code. This way it would keep track of the extended code size and automatically make every jump, offset and such correct. Another possibility could be to get the same support in the linker instead. The advantage of this would be that it might be possible to profile all the code, even code from third part where there not is any access to the source code.
- * When I collected profiling data I hooked up the phone to a logic analyzer. This limits both the amount of profiling that can be retrieved and the generality of the data (it is only one or a few users that make operations on the phone, who knows what other users might do). A better solution would be if the profiling-data could be saved in the phone it self, and then later retrieved. This way many “profiling-phones” could be distributed to different kind of users, and they could use the phone for a long time period. This would give much more profiling data and make it more general. However, the profiling data then had to be saved to the file system in the phone and that would slow down the execution substantially, but there might be a way around this. The information wanted is a counter on every call made between two specific functions. My investigation indicates that there would have to be around 50000-100000 counters, the data size of this would then be 1.5 – 3 MB (if 4 byte integers are used), so the size of the data wouldn’t be a problem. But still there is the problem of slow execution. This could be solved by, for example, only recording every 128th call. To do this there could be another counter (resident in memory) that would be added on every call, and if that counter have specific bits set then the counter on secondary memory would be added. To not have to search for the counter that should be added there can be constant offsets programmed into the profiling-code. Because of the vast quantity of profiling-data that could be retrieved with this method it doesn’t matter that only every 128th call is recorded, the result would even out anyway.

Then there is the next phase; to rearrange the code. I only did a simulation of this, but if it is going to be done for real I think that there have to be support for it in the linker. The linker then would get a list of the wanted order of functions as input and place the executable accordingly on the address space. But this may cause yet another problem with short jumps; the linker would have to change those jumps to long ones, which might not be possible.

6 CONCLUSION AND FURTHER RESEARCH

In this thesis I have studied if and to what extent it is possible to reduce the amount of page faults in a demand paging environment by rearranging functions on secondary memory. The functions were rearranged based on profiling. How to obtain this profiling from a real time critical system has also been a big part of this thesis.

As further research there are mainly two things that have crossed my mind:

- * I concentrated my efforts on rearranging whole functions. This yielded very satisfying results, but even better might be possible if one breaks down the functions to basic blocks and make procedure splitting, as described by Pettis and Hansen [1].
- * When I collected profiling-data I only used the information about how many times a specific function called another specific function. More information may help a function-positioning algorithm to achieve better results. For example if two functions often is executed after each other (but not call each other).

The conclusion is that to optimize the code layout on secondary memory has great potential. My results talk for them self (in average 20 - 40% decrease in the amount of page faults). And on basis on the material in this area of research that I have read, we only so far have scratched the surface. More effective algorithms for rearranging code will by no doubt be invented.

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